

Wards Through Time: A Comparative Analysis of Urban Development, Ranchi City, India

Paper Id : 19230 Submission Date : 2024-07-09 Acceptance Date : 2024-07-22 Publication Date : 2024-07-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13757419

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Abstract The study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of urban development within the context of evolving wards, localities, and colonies. Focusing on key factors such as geographical location, physical attributes, land use patterns, population dynamics, and related indicators, this research paper endeavors to elucidate the intricate relationship between these elements and the overarching process of urbanization.

Drawing upon the case study of Ranchi City, the research paper examines eight distinct wards that span multiple localities and demonstrate varying land use and land cover characteristics. By tracing the evolution of these wards across different time periods, ranging from the period prior to the formation of the Jharkhand state to the present day, the chapter offers valuable insights into the transformations induced by urbanization. The comparative analysis sheds light on the shifts in resources, vegetation, settlement patterns, and broader land use dynamics that have occurred over time.

Through a synthesis of geographical information, historical data, and urban development trends, the chapter contributes to a deeper understanding of the multifaceted impacts of urbanization on localities. The exploration of changing land use patterns and their implications not only enhances our comprehension of urban development trajectories but also provides essential knowledge for sustainable urban planning and resource management.

Keywords Urbanization, Landuse/ Land Cover, Resources, Vegetation, Settlement.

Introduction The study of urban development is an intricate endeavor, characterized by the dynamic interplay of historical legacies, geographical constraints, socioeconomic forces, and governance policies. Within this intricate tapestry, the city of Ranchi stands as a compelling case study, offering unique insights into the nuanced evolution of urban landscapes. This chapter contributes to the comprehensive understanding of urban dynamics by focusing on the city's wards as distinctive units of analysis. By examining the comparative trajectories of urban development across different wards of Ranchi, we illuminate the multifaceted factors that have shaped the city's growth over time.

Ranchi, the capital of Jharkhand state in India, is a city of rich historical significance, where tradition intertwines with modernity and where the influences of industrialization, migration, and technological advancement have left their indelible mark. The ward-based approach allows us to delve beyond the broader urban narrative and uncover hidden patterns, inequalities, and developmental shifts that might otherwise be overlooked. Each ward carries a unique historical, cultural, and socioeconomic context, contributing to the mosaic of Ranchi's urban fabric.

The central focus of this study is to provide a meticulous analysis of the diverse factors influencing the developmental trajectories of Ranchi's wards. Through the lens of historical records, geographical information systems (GIS) data, census figures, and urban planning documents, we construct a temporal narrative that traces the evolution of the city. By comparing the development of different wards, we seek to identify the converging and diverging forces that have shaped their growth patterns.

The implications of this research reach beyond the confines of Ranchi. Urban centers worldwide grapple with challenges related to sustainable growth, equitable resource distribution, and effective governance. Lessons drawn from the comparative analysis of

Ranchi's wards offer valuable insights for urban planners, policymakers, and researchers globally. The nuanced understanding of developmental processes at the ward level can guide efforts toward creating more inclusive, resilient, and harmonious urban environments.

In the subsequent sections of this paper, we detail the methodology employed for data collection and analysis, contextualize Ranchi's urban evolution within its historical and geographical milieu, present the findings of the comparative analysis across wards, and conclude with a discussion on the broader implications and potential applications of the insights gained. By immersing ourselves in the story of Ranchi's urban development, we contribute to the growing body of knowledge on urban studies and offer a framework that can be applied to similar analyses in diverse urban contexts.

Objective of study

The objectives of the present study are:

1. To identify and compare the changes in urbanization and land use patterns in Ranchi City before and after the year 2000, analyzing the trends up to the present.
2. To analyze the resulting pressure on land resources due to urbanization across different wards of Ranchi City, focusing on spatial impacts.
3. To formulate strategies to address the challenges posed by urbanization, with an emphasis on sustainable land resource management in Ranchi City.

Review of Literature

Singh and Singh¹ (1988) had picked certain financial parameters to characterize urbanization and were of the view that urbanization implied the extent of aggregate populace 10 packed in urban settlements. It is additionally the outflow of the contemporary political, social, financial, and social procedures winning in a district.

Mandal² (1998) gives a broad meaning of urbanization. He utilized certain statistical, social, and monetary parameters and had classified them into four factors in clarifying urbanization. These elements incorporate (a) centralization of people in one place (b) populace move (relocation) from a provincial to an urban area (c) word-related move from agribusiness to non-horticulture and (d) land utilization move from farming to non-farming.

Urbanization does not happen equitably finished space and time, since forms prompting urbanization change starting with one district then onto the next and starting with one-time frame then onto the next.

Rapid unplanned urban growth has transformed cities into clusters of asphalt, concrete, brick, and impervious surfaces³, replacing natural forests⁴ and agricultural land⁵. This frequently leads to a decrease in soil moisture and evapotranspiration^{6,7,8} and releases significant amounts of waste heat into the urban atmosphere, which can disrupt the appearance of micro and mesoscale climates^{9,10}.

Methodology

The study is based on satellite data analysis using remote sensing and GIS techniques. Satellite imageries have been acquired from the USGS (United States Geological Survey) and NRSC (National Remote Sensing Centre). There is limitation in availability of oldest and latest time period satellite imagery of the region.

There are several ways to classify the imagery in different land use and land cover. One method is digital classification using supervised or unsupervised classification. In this supervised classification have higher accuracy and proved to be useful in most of the cases. Another method is visual classification. For visual classification of land use land cover of the region Green, Red, and Near-Infrared bands of Landsat were primarily used. Other bands were also used to discriminate different features. Using these bands' false color composites (FCC), true colour composites were made and visually analyzed, and classified. The number of classes was as follows-

1. Open Field
2. Water Body-Lake, Pond, River
3. WasteLand
4. Vegetation
5. Settlement

Result and Discussion

Map - 1.1
Ward No. :- 1 (Land use and Land cover)

Source: Year 1999 & 2004 maps are Prepared from Landsat Imagery, USGS & Years 2014 & 2024 maps are prepared from LISS III, NRSC

Ward number 1 includes areas of Kantatoli, Kanke Road, Chandway Basti, Chandwe, Jhiringatoli, Tikali Toli, Vasant Vihar (Kanke Road), etc.

In this map, land use and land cover are shown in the above-mentioned areas (ward-1) in different years.

From the above map, We observed that in 1999, in this particular ward, there was dense vegetation even though there was an enormous availability of water by Kanke dam. In the southern part of the ward, there is some areas of wasteland and in the northeastern part, there are settlements due to the availability of water and fertile land.

In 2004, we can see that in the Northern portion of the ward, there was a decrease in vegetation as settlement area have increased and there is also a decrease in water

networks in the northern parts of the ward.

In 2014, there was huge growth in the settlement area, it is shown that settlement area has increased all over the area and there is less amount of area available for vegetation which is in the southern part of the ward and there is a small portion of wasteland is also available at the northern part of the ward.

In 2024,vegetation have lessen due to increase in settlement area and urbanization. Even the settlement area has now occupied some areas of wasteland. One of the newly developed areas is comes under this ward is Kanke Road. In Kanke Road and its adjacent areas like Jhirkatoli, Vasant Vihar etc are having highly modernized infrastructures. Within 10 years of time period (2014-2024) there were lots of new malls, restaurants, and residential complexes developed. It is a negative sign for Land resources because due to infrastructural development vegetation cover area and agricultural land decreases.

Map – 1.2
WARD NO. :- 3 (Land use and Land cover)

Source: Year 1999 & 2004 maps are Prepared from Landsat Imagery, USGS & Years 2014 & 2024 maps are prepared from LISS III, NRSC

Ward number 3 of Ranchi City includes areas of Morbadi, Chiraundi, Tagore Hill Road (Morabadi), Adalhatu, Sindwar Toli, Bhitha Adalhatu, etc. There are some areas under this ward. In this map, Land cover is shown of the above-mentioned areas in different years.

From the above map, we observed that in 1999 in this particular ward, the vegetation was moderate neither too dense nor too thin, and in some areas amid the vegetation, there are waste of land, but largely wastelands were on the northern portion of the ward.

The water bodies are available in most of the areas but it is in the middle of the ward and the north-eastern part of the areas of easy access to water. So, we can see that largely compact settlements are in the center and semi-compact in the northern part of the ward and dispersed settlement is scattered all over the ward. In some areas of wasteland, there are open fields, in the southern portion of the ward.

In 2004, we can see that, the areas of wasteland are occupied by settlement and even there is less number of water bodies comparatively than in year 1999. In this map, we can see that the settlement area has increased and a little bit of vegetation has also increased in the north-western part of the ward.

In 2014, it can be seen that the settlement was still continuously increasing due to the rapid increase in urbanization which resulted in a decline in vegetation and the wasteland occupied by settlement areas. In the south, there are some open fields.

In 2024, still, the settlement continuously increasing and a large portion of open fields are also occupied. The water bodies have also lessen due to increase in settlement area, and even open fields are occupied.

Map - 1.3
WARD NO. :- 11 (Land use and Land cover)

Source: Year 1999 & 2004 maps are Prepared from Landsat Imagery, USGS & Years 2014 & 2024 maps are prepared from LISS III, NRSC

Ward number 11 of Ranchi City includes areas Kantatoli, Kantatoli(Sultan Lane), Kantatoli (Purulia Road), Khorha toli (Kokar), Purulia Road Azad Basti, Lowadih, Purana Lowadih, Samlong etc are some areas under this ward. In this map, land use and land cover are shown in the above-mentioned areas in different years.

From the above map, we observed that in 1999, in this particular ward, the vegetation was in the southwestern part of the ward and in the northern part of this ward. Settlements was also located where there was vegetation, especially in the south-western part. In the midst of the ward there was wasteland and on the outer part of the wasteland, there was water sources surrounding most of the area.

In 2004, we can see that there was no change, largely in the areas of settlement, vegetation, and wasteland but there was a drastic change in water resources. The water resources completely disappeared which can be seen from the map of 1999 to 2004 and a small portion can be seen in the southern part.

In 2014, it can be seen that the settlement area increased in the southwestern part and dispersed settlement was spread in some of the areas of the north. Due to the increase in settlement area, the vegetation has declined.

In 2024, the settlement still continues to increase which leads to the decline of vegetation and wasteland. The settlement has increased in the southwestern part of the ward, which is largely compact, and scattered settlements can be seen in the northern and north-eastern parts of the ward.

Map - 1.4
WARD NO. :- 19 (Land use and Land cover)

Source: Year 1999 & 2004 maps are Prepared from Landsat Imagery, USGS & Years 2014 & 2024 maps are prepared from LISS III, NRSC

Ward number 19 of Ranchi City includes areas of Bharat Puri (Purulia Road), Lalpur, P.N. Bose compound, Circular Road, Thadpakhna (Lohara Kocha), H.B Road, Chadri, East Jail Road, Line Tank Road, etc, areas are under this ward

In this map, land use and land cover is shown in the above-mentioned areas.

From this map, we can observe that in the year 1999 in the ward no. 19, the vegetation was in the midst of this ward and the settlement was surrounded it from most of the areas except the west. There were also some water sources near the settlement areas and over the vegetation area. There was also a small portion of wasteland in some parts of the ward.

In 2004, we can see a huge difference from the map of 1999 as the settlement area which was surrounding the vegetation has now occupied a large area of the vegetation cover and the small portion of wasteland which was available in 1999 was also occupied by settlement area and some leftovers were in the northern part of the ward. Even the water sources also have lessened due to the increase in settlement area.

In 2014, the settlement area continued to grow due to which, the areas of vegetation and wasteland have decreased. The vegetation cover was mainly in the northwestern part of the ward. The water sources can be seen mainly scattered over the southern part and some areas of the north.

In 2024, we can see that there is hardly any changes if we compare the map of 2014, but the vegetation cover has growth.

Map - 1.5
WARD NO. :- 26 (Land use and Land cover)

Source: Year 1999 & 2004 maps are Prepared from Landsat Imagery, USGS & Years 2014 & 2024 maps are prepared from LISS III, NRSC

Ward number 26 of Ranchi City includes Hindpiri, Gowal Toli, Masjid Gali, Tewari Tank Road, Bnai Raja Lane, Qudrattullah Lane, Pee Pee Compound etc are the areas which come under this ward.

In this map, we can observe that in 1999, in this ward the area was covered under settlement and vegetation can be seen in the south of this ward, and in some areas there were some water sources.

In 2004, there was hardly any change but the settlement area has increased in the southern part of this ward due to which the vegetation cover has lessen in that part. There can be also a small portion of wasteland and some sources of water in the north of this ward.

In 2014, we can see that the vegetation cover continued to decline due to an increase in settlement area, and the wasteland completely disappeared.

In 2024, we can see that there is no prominent change but it can be observed that the vegetation coverage area has reduced as compared to other years. So, in this way, we clearly visualize the changes in the last two decades. This area has been densely populated since 1999 but after the formation of the Jharkhand state, this area has also undergone urbanizational pressure. Newly developed residential apartments, malls, and multiplexes are seen in the Pee Pee compound area but the entire ward is affected by the pressure of urbanization. The land resource is one of the vital resources for human life but day-to-day rapid increase in urbanization deteriorated not only the land resource but also the climate of the Ranchi city. It also affects the soil quality, increases air pollution, and noise pollution, releases CFC gases, etc. This area is the adjacent area of the main road which is why this particular area receives maximum pressure. Rapid increase in urbanization is the matter of concern not only for land resource but its also directly impacts on Ranchi city's climate.

Map - 1.6
WARD NO. :- 32 (Land use and Land cover)

Source: Year 1999 & 2004 maps are Prepared from Landsat Imagery, USGS & Years 2014 & 2024 maps are prepared from LISS III, NRSC

Ward number 32 of Ranchi city includes Indrapuri, Alkapuri (Ratu Road), Ratu Road, Seopuri, Aryapuri, Arya Nagar, Kathar Gonda, Kanke Road (Opposite CM. House), Barihi Mohalla, Sukhdeo Nagar (Ratu Road), etc are the areas which come under this ward.

From this map, we can observe in 1999, mainly the area was covered with vegetation, and in the southern and south-western parts of this ward settlement can be seen, and water sources were also located near the settlement area. There was some areas of wasteland and open spaces in the middle of the ward.

In 2004 we can see that there is a huge difference in the settlement area, it has now occupied the vegetation cover, and most parts of the southern and south-western parts of this ward are occupied by settlement.

The growth of settlement have also affected the water resources of this area, as comparatively in the year 1999 there were more water bodies than in the year 2004. In the middle of this ward, there was an open space and a little area of wasteland in the northeastern part.

In 2014, it can be seen that the settlement continued to grow and it has also occupied some areas of north and northeast of this ward and scattered settlement can be seen in the south-eastern part. Some of the water sources can be seen in the southern part and the wasteland and open spaces have lessened due to the increase in urbanization.

In 2024, it can be seen that due to urbanization there was a rapid growth in settlement which resulted in the decline of vegetation. The vegetation cover can be seen in the northern and south eastern of this ward. Some open spaces are also available in the northern and southwestern parts.

Map - 1.7
WARD NO. :- 51 (Land use and Land cover)

Source: Year 1999 & 2004 maps are Prepared from Landsat Imagery, USGS & Years 2014 & 2024 maps are prepared from LISS III, NRSC

Ward number 51 of Ranchi City includes Doranda, Kadru (New Area), Kusai, Laxmi Para etc are some areas that come under this ward.

From this map, we can observe that in 1999, this ward was largely covered with settlements. There were only some areas in the north which was having vegetation cover and in areas of northeast and southwest of this ward there was a small portion of the wasteland and there are also some sources of water scattered in this ward.

In 2004, we can see that the settlement area continued to grow because of which the vegetation cover and water resources have also lessened and there is also a decrease in the area of wasteland in the northeastern part.

In 2014, we can see that the major difference was only in the vegetation cover as it can be seen in some areas which is comparatively less than the other years and the wasteland has also lessened because of the increase in the settlement area.

In 2024 also, we can see that because of rapid growth in the settlement area, the vegetation cover has declined and a small portion of wasteland was left. The water sources were also affected due to this rapid growth in settlement which can be seen as there are very few water sources available.

Map - 1.8
WARD NO. :- 52 (Land use and Land cover)

Source: Year 1999 & 2004 maps are Prepared from Landsat Imagery, USGS & Years 2014 & 2024 maps are prepared from LISS III, NRSC

Ward number 52 of Ranchi City includes areas of New Saket Nagar, Khokma Toli, Pokhar Toli (Hinoo), Hundru Part, Mani Tola, Hara Tand, Rahmat Colony etc are areas which comes under this ward.

From the above map, we can observe that in 1999, this ward was largely covered with wasteland. But there were areas in the northern and southeast parts where vegetation can be seen. The areas where vegetation was located near the water sources are also available. Largely vegetation can be seen in the northwestern part of the ward and here settlements were also located. Settlements are prominently located in the northwestern and southwestern parts of the ward. There was also a small portion of open space available.

In 2004, we can see that the settlement area as well as the vegetation cover shows growth but the water resources shows a negative growth but the water resources shows a negative growth and it can be seen only in the centre and some areas of

south eastern part of this ward. The vegetation cover have increased in the areas of north – western and south – eastern part. Settlement has also increased in the western part of this ward. There is also growth in open field areas. Due to the increase in these, the wasteland area has declined.

In 2014, we can see that the settlement area continues to increase in the northwestern and southwestern parts, and scattered settlements also can be seen spread all over this ward. There was also an increase in open fields.

In 2024, we can see that the settlement area has growing in a rapid rate as within the span of 10 years it has occupied most of the areas of wasteland and some portion of vegetation cover. The open fields also show an increase in area.

Conclusion

In conclusion, over the past two decades, Ranchi has transformed into a city with a population exceeding a million, becoming the administrative capital of Jharkhand state. The transformation initiated a rapid surge in infrastructural development post-2000. A comprehensive analysis of various factors, including satellite images spanning from 1999 to 2024, on-site observations, investigations, and interviews with residents, reveals that the repercussions of urbanization manifest negatively in several dimensions, particularly exerting pressure on land resources. The erstwhile dominant agricultural sector has witnessed a significant decline in both cultivated land area and crop production, as evidenced by land use and land cover maps and satellite imagery of Ranchi City.

However, amidst these challenges, there are pockets where residents view urbanization positively, perceiving it as a catalyst for improved living standards. This positive perspective often comes at the expense of agricultural land loss and environmental impact. Residents in these areas appreciate the positive changes brought about by urbanization, notably in the form of enhanced infrastructure, such as the construction of roads, which were previously absent. Notably, the shift from agriculture to non-agricultural activities has led to a decline in the number of agricultural laborers, indicating the transformative influence of urbanization on the local economy.

Suggestions for the future Study

1. The Rain Water Harvesting should be mandatory for all new and old infrastructural developments in the Ranchi Municipal Corporation area.
2. All infrastructure should be constructed on pillars and there should be open space left for absorption of ground water underneath the building. So it will eventually lead to an increase in groundwater table.

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